

THE STUDY OF THE MEANING OF THE WORD TOLERANCE IN OTHER LANGUAGES

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Tolerance has always been considered to be the most important aspect in human's life. Tolerance helps people live in peace and harmony while at the same time making their dreams come true. Tolerance is an important concept that helps people live in peace. Being tolerant means that you accept other people's opinions and preferences, even if they live in a way you don't agree with. Tolerance also means that you don't put your own opinion above the opinion of others, even if you're sure you're right. Tolerant people show their strength by being able to deal with different opinions.

What is tolerance?

Tolerance (from the Latin *tolerantia* - "patience, patience, ability to endure") is a sociological term denoting tolerance for a different worldview, lifestyle, behavior and customs. Tolerance is not the same as indifference. It also does not mean the adoption of a different worldview or way of life; it consists in giving others the right to live in accordance with their own worldview.

Tolerance is the appreciation of diversity and the ability to live and let others live. It is the ability to exercise a fair and objective attitude towards those whose opinions, practices, religion, nationality, and so on differ from one's own. As William Ury notes, "tolerance is not just agreeing with one another or remaining indifferent in the face of injustice, but rather showing respect for the essential humanity in every person."

Intolerance is the failure to appreciate and respect the practices, opinions and beliefs of another group. For instance, there is a high degree of intolerance between Israeli Jews and Palestinians who are at odds over issues of identity, security, self-determination, statehood, the right of return for refugees, the status of Jerusalem and many other issues. The result is continuing intergroup conflict and violence.

The Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary defines this concept as follows:

Tolerance - tolerance for a different kind of views, mores, habits.

The sound of the word "tolerance" in different languages of the globe: French - an attitude in which it is allowed that others may think differently or act.

French - an attitude in which it is allowed that others may think differently or act differently than you yourself;

English - willingness to be tolerant, indulgent;

Chinese - allow, accept, be generous towards others;

Arabic - forgiveness, indulgence, gentleness, mercy, compassion, patience.

Russian - to be able to put up with the existence of something.

Spanish - the ability to recognize ideas or opinions that are different from one's own.

Saying tolerance in European Languages

Language	Ways to say tolerance
Albanian	tolerancë
English	tolerance
Basque	tolerantzia
Belorussian	talent
Bulgarian	tolerance
Bosnian	tolerancija
Welsh	goddefgarwch

Saying tolerance in Asian Languages.

Language	Ways to say tolerance
Azerbaijani	tolerantlıq
Armenian	հանդուրժողականություն
Bengal	সহ্য
Vietnamese	lòng khoan dung

REFERENCES:

1. ПРОГРАММА «ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ -ПОТРЕБНОСТЬ НАШЕГО ВРЕМЕНИ» 2001
2. <http://www.nikolsk.shkola.hc.ru/page-74.html>
3. <https://www.unesco.org/en>
4. <https://www.tsutmb.ru>